

6-Sulpho-*m*-cresotic Acid and Related Compounds.

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In view of the fact that 6-chlorocresotic acid is a more powerful antiseptic than the 5-chloro compound, 6-sulphocresotic acid (I) has been prepared by the sulphonation of *m*-cresotic acid. The constitution (I) follows from its conversion to (II) by bromination and the subsequent hydrolysis of (II) into (III).

(III) on nitration gave (IV) identical with 4:6-dinitro-2-bromo-*m*-cresol (Gibbs and Robertson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1886). The compounds (V) and (VI), prepared as indicated on the diagrammatic scheme, also support the constitution (I) of sulpho acid. The bromo-cresotic acid of Gattermann (*Ber.*, 1893, 26, 1851), which he prepared from a nitro-*m*-cresotic acid, is identical with the above acid and hence it is 2-bromo-*m*-cresotic acid and not the 6-bromo-acid as was supposed by him. Walther and Zipper's bromo acid, m.p. 221°, (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1915, ii, 91, 364) is different from Gattermann's acid.

When brominated in acetic acid (II) gives (VI) by extrusion of the sulphonic group. In dilute acetic acid solution, the carboxy group even is eliminated resulting in tribromo-*m*-cresol. Use of 20% hydrobromic acid avoids these extrusions of groups.

Nitration of (I) with dilute nitric acid at 60° or in acetic acid at 30° gives 6-nitro-*m*-cresotic acid (Einhorn, *Annalen*, 1900, **311**, 477) and in sulphuric acid with a mixture of nitric and sulphuric acids, dinitro-*m*-cresotic acid is obtained, while the sulphonitro-*m*-cresotic acid is obtained only when nitration is carried out in fuming sulphuric acid with a mixture of fuming nitric and sulphuric acids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

6-Sulpho-m-cresotic Acid.—*m*-Cresotic acid (40 g.) was slowly dissolved at room temperature in sulphuric acid (60 c.c., 100%). The sulphonic acid separated completely in about 24 hours. It crystallised from water either in needles or plates, m.p. 93°. (Found: Equiv., 152.0. $C_8H_8O_6S, 4H_2O$ requires Equiv., 152.1).

The *Acid Potassium Salt* crystallised from water in white slender needles. (Found: K, 12.1; H_2O , 16.4; Equiv., 322.0. $C_8H_7O_6SK, 3H_2O$ requires K, 12.0; H_2O , 16.7 per cent. Equiv., 324.3).

The *Acid Sodium Salt* crystallised in slender needles from water. (Found: Na, 8.6; H_2O , 6.7; Equiv., 272.8. $C_8H_7O_6SNa, H_2O$ requires Na, 8.5; H_2O , 6.6 per cent. Equiv., 272.1).

The *Acid Calcium Salt* crystallised from water in small needles. [Found: Ca, 6.3; Equiv., 292.9. $(C_8H_7O_6S)_2 Ca, 5H_2O$ requires Ca, 6.7 per cent. Equiv., 296.1].

The *Acid Barium Salt* crystallises from water. [Found: Ba, 19.8; Equiv., 343.6. $(C_8H_7O_6S)_2 Ba, 5H_2O$ requires Ba, 19.9 per cent. Equiv., 344.7.)

The *Methyl Ether*.—(i) Methyl ether of *m*-cresotic acid (20 g.) was dissolved in fuming sulphuric acid (25 g.) at room temperature and then heated at 60° for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The sulphonic acid separated on absorbing moisture from air for three days. It was filtered through flannel and crystallised from water in needles or plates, m.p. 193° (decomp.). (Found: Equiv., 140.7. $C_9H_{10}O_6S, 2H_2O$ requires Equiv., 141.0).

(ii) It was also prepared by adding dimethylsulphate (200 c.c.) to a solution of sulpho-*m*-cresotic acid (25 g.) in sodium hydroxide solution (25%) at room temperature, until the reaction mixture gave no colour with ferric chloride, then heating on sand-bath for 2 hours, cooling and acidifying. (Found: Na, 7.6; H_2O , 11.3; Equiv., 305.6. $C_8H_9O_6SNa, 2H_2O$ requires Na, 7.6; H_2O , 11.8; per cent. Equiv., 304.0).

2:4:6-Tribromo-m-cresol, prepared by bubbling bromine vapour

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(9 g.) through an aqueous solution of sulpho-*m*-cresotic acid (5 g.), crystallises as slender needles, m.p. 84°, (*cf.* Errera, *Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2791; *J. pr. Chem.*, 1889, 39, 59). (Found: Equiv., 339.2; Calc. for $C_7H_5OBr_3$: Equiv., 344.9).

2:6-Dibromo-m-cresotic Acid was obtained as a flocculent precipitate by bubbling bromine vapour (6 g.) through a solution of sulphonic acid in dilute hydrobromic acid (22%). It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in slender needles, m.p. 234-35°. It is identical with the compound prepared by Errera (*Ber.*, 1899, 32, 2791) and by Eihorn and Ehret (*Annalen*, 1897, 295, 180). (Found: Equiv., 308.8. Calc. for $C_8H_6O_3Br_2$: Equiv., 309.9.)

2-Bromo-6-sulpho-m-cresotic Acid.—Bromine (9 g.) was bubbled through a solution of sulphonic acid (15 g.) in hydrobromic acid (100 c.c., 45%). After having removed the solid, which was 2:6-dibromocresotic acid, the mother liquor was treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid and placed in a freezing mixture, when the sulpho-bromo-*m* cresotic acid separated out. It crystallised from hot water in slender needles, m.p. 183°. The yields are improved if the bromination is carried out at 0°, instead of 30°, or stronger hydrobromic acid is used as solvent. (Found: Br, 22.4; Equiv., 182.5. $C_8H_7O_6BrS$, $3H_2O$ requires Br, 21.9 per cent. Equiv., 182.5).

The Acid Potassium Salt crystallised in slender needles from hot water. (Found: K, 10.2; Equiv., 367.2. $C_8H_6O_6BrSK$, H_2O requires K, 10.6 per cent. Equiv., 367.1)

The Acid Calcium Salt crystallised from boiling water in granules. [Found: Ca, 5.8; Equiv., 329.9. $(C_8H_6O_6SBr)_2Ca$ requires Ca, 6.1 per cent. Equiv., 330.1].

2-Bromo-m-cresotic Acid was prepared by distilling a solution of 2-bromo-6-sulpho-*m*-cresotic acid (5 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (90 c.c.) with superheated steam at 150°, until a solid began to separate in the distillate. It is sparingly soluble in cold water, but soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and water. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid as leaflets, m.p. 211°, yield 3 g. (Found: Br, 34.7; Equiv., 230.9. $C_8H_7O_3Br$ requires Br, 34.6 per cent. Equiv., 231.0).

The Sodium Salt crystallised from water in shining plates. (Found: Na, 7.6. $C_8H_6O_3BrNa$, $2H_2O$ requires Na, 7.9 per cent).

The Potassium Salt crystallised from water in slender white needles or scales. (Found: K, 14.4. $C_8H_6O_3BrK$ requires K, 14.5 per cent).

The Methyl ether.—Bromine vapour (6 g.) was bubbled through a solution of methyl ether of 6-sulpho-*m*-cresotic acid (10 g.) in hydro-

bromic acid (40%, 50 c.c.). It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in needles, m.p. 137-38°. (Found : Equiv., 246.5. $C_9H_9O_3Br$ requires Equiv., 244.9).

The Barium Salt is sparingly soluble in water and difficult to crystallise. [Found : Ba, 20.4; H_2O , 5.2. $(C_9H_8O_3Br)_2 Ba, 2H_2O$ requires Ba, 20.7; H_2O , 5.4 per cent].

2: 6-Dinitro-*m*-cresotic Acid.—A mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) and fuming nitric acid (10 c.c.) was added drop by drop with constant stirring to a solution of 6-sulpho-*m*-cresotic acid (20 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (30 c.c.) in a freezing mixture. After the reaction was complete the mixture was poured over powdered ice and the precipitate was recrystallised from dilute acetic acid in cubes, m.p. 185° (dinitro-*m*-cresotic acid); while the 2-nitro-6-sulpho-*m*-cresotic acid could be recovered from the mother liquor as the barium salt. A slight rise in the temperature gave dinitro-*m*-cresotic acid as the main product, while above 70°, it gave trinitro-*m*-cresol, m.p. 105°.

2-Nitro-6-sulpho-*m*-cresotic Acid.—A mixture of fuming nitric acid (5 g.) and fuming sulphuric acid (30 g.) was added drop by drop to *m*-cresotic acid (15 g.) dissolved in fuming sulphuric acid (50 g.) at room temperature when the nitrosulpho-*m*-cresotic acid crystallised out. It crystallises from hot water in slender needles, m.p. 85°.

The Barium Salt was obtained by treating the mother liquor from the above experiment with barium carbonate. It crystallises in pale yellow needles from water. (Found : S, 6.5; Ba, 28.4. $C_8H_5O_8NSBa, 4H_2O$ requires S, 6.6; Ba, 28.3 per cent).

The Calcium Salt crystallises in slender, pale yellow needles. (Found : Ca, 10.40. $C_8H_5O_8NS Ca, 4H_2O$ requires Ca, 10.3 per cent).